

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Results and Summary of the START Delphi Survey Round 1

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Introduction to the START Delphi Survey

The START project deployed the Delphi survey as a complementary foresight tool to measure the maturity of the project concept, providing chances for potential improvements that might become necessary along the project evolution, with major focus on the technological, business and economy aspects. The Delphi survey methodology has been designed as a forecasting technique to support technological development and implementation for many technology lines. The main aim is to drive the participants to a consensus on different topics, throughout statements and questions, made in two or more rounds. This technique is anonymous, building on group communication, so that the process is effective in allowing a group of individuals, as a whole, to deal with a complex problem or question (Linstone and Turoff, 2002). In a Delphi process, experts (the participants) are asked to consider and classify a number of questions or statements.

The Delphi process is different from other types of surveys and questionnaires. First, a list of relevant interested experts is pre-compiled. Second, there is a possibility for experts to comment and explain their opinion on any of the statements. Third, answers are analysed, statistics built and shared with the experts for further comments, resulting in new rounds of questions. Finally, the objective of a Delphi is to reach a consensus within the expert pool.

The START Delphi Survey was built in two rounds between the months of October 2023 and April 2024, with round 1 running between October and November 2023 and round 2 between March and April 2024. It was used as a way to engage with experts and collect their views and opinions in areas of interest to START and that are relevant for the project development both during and after the funding period. The survey ultimately addressed the current and future states of the thermoelectric field and the future of START, as a new technology line based on tetrahedrite thermoelectric modules and systems, entwined with topics such as sustainability, energy generation and economics.

This document presents the Delphi Survey Round 1 statements and questions, and the opinions and views of experts.

Statement 1: The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is the future of renewable energy and circular economy.

Summary: Experts came to a general agreement that the implementation of thermoelectric energy production is one of the great possibilities to generate green energy and contribute to the circular economy. The responses highlight several perspectives on the role of thermoelectric devices in the future of renewable energy. Some believe TE will have a place in the family of renewable energies, with a focus on thermal energy harvesting for industrial digitalization, combined use of waste heat for electric power and domestic heating, with low and highgrade heat harvesting using TE seen as a priority, aligned with EU targets for sustainable heavy industry. The importance of utilizing waste heat, especially in the current context of substantial waste heat generation, is emphasized for clean energy and energy circularity. Others expressed their concerns on the application of TE regarding cost-efficiency and, heat-to-electricity sustainable manufacturing. Furthermore, TE devices although acknowledged as one option for converting waste heat into electricity, are perceived as limited to specific niche applications.

Statement 2: Sustainable thermoelectric devices would unblock the application of thermoelectrics in many fields, despite lower performance.

Summary: In general, experts agree that the development and implementation of more sustainable thermoelectric devices, when compared to the current ones, would greatly change the way the technology is seen by end-users and society at large. Despite this, experts highlight a few bottlenecks that need to

be solved before TE is implemented at large, including materials and device stability, aging effects, and the critical need for sustainability to justify investments in thermoelectric development. Cost, production methods, and material source sustainability play a crucial role in making thermoelectrics attractive for various fields and the primary barriers to large-scale adoption identified are performance (conversion efficiency), cost, and scalability, with an emphasis on the availability and non-toxicity of materials. While the technology is seen as holding promise for applications like powering IoT sensor networks, its limitations in generating sufficient electric power for many fields are noted. A final remark is that higher performance remains essential for adoption in various applications.

Statement 3: One solution-fits-all is not feasible for thermoelectric devices and applications.

Summary: Experts tend to agree that the best approach for the development of TE devices is not to develop one overall solution, but rather develop specific devices for specific temperature ranges. Experts state that temperature dependence of material and device performances, along with the need for design optimization, makes it challenging to achieve a "one solutionfits-all" approach. They list temperature range, cost, reliability, and customization options as factors that impact the design of thermoelectric generators. Experts also mention that applications vary in thermal load and environmental conditions, requiring a holistic consideration of materials and device architecture for optimal performance.

Statement 4: Using tetrahedrite materials sourced from mining tailings recovery will mitigate the competition between thermoelectric and other electronic devices.

Summary: The use of tetrahedrite materials for TE devices is rather divisive. The strategy of producing thermoelectric materials directly from waste mineral tetrahedrites is considered promising from the perspectives of sustainability, waste valorization, and critical materials management. The potential benefits identified include cost reduction compared to traditional mining and processing methods for other minerals and materials. However, experts also mention that the success of the START project in particular hinges on the complexity and cost-effectiveness of processing minerals, especially in terms of tailing recovery impact on thermoelectric generator efficiency, reliability, and reproducibility, which are not yet proven and require project results for a better assessment.

Statement 5: Applications using thermoelectric devices based on tetrahedrites will be on the market by 2030.

Summary: Experts agree that tetrahedrite based TE devices will hit the market successfully in the future, but they disagree towards the timeframe for that to happen. Some experts state that development of thermoelectric technology depends on the effort and resources applied, taking several years to develop from materials to devices. However, they also suggest that the key towards market implementation of a TE technology lies in matching promising materials with the right applications, considering factors like source and heat flux density, together with the operating temperature and the discovery of potential n-

type materials to couple with the tetrahedrites. Tetrahedrite shows promise for low to medium temperatures applications, utilizing cost-effective materials, but competition with other mid-temperature materials like half-heuslers and skutterudites might hinder marketization. Finally, some caution is advised, as successful commercialization of TE devices is still to be assessed in the future as the survival of companies producing them is still uncertain as the last years have proven.

Statement 6: The START innovation ecosystem would be of interest to me.

Summary: Experts found that the START work and the value chain that it is developing, built around the use of tetrahedrites, would be of great interest to them. The project is viewed as an opportunity to contribute to sustainable thermoelectrics, waste heat recovery, and the generation of green energy from electronic devices produced through tailings recovery, which is a unique process. Experts emphasize the importance of successful development for further industrialization, involving various relevant players to meet performance, cost, scalability, integration, sales, and improvement requirements.

Question 1: What kinds of devices or applications, in the short, medium and long-term, utilise thermoelectricity?

Summary: Experts' answers identify a broad range of applications for thermoelectric devices in various industries and sectors. In summary, they suggest that thermoelectric technology finds, or will find applications across various sectors, including industry, automotive, wearables, IoT, and space, with an emphasis on waste heat recovery, power generation, and electronic cooling. The applications include:

- Industrial Sector: Waste heat recovery systems in industries with considerable waste heat and power generation to provide energy to devices (e.g. safety devices in industry to prevent contact burns); Power supplies for district heating, heat exchanger monitoring, pumping monitoring, construction monitoring, environmental sensors, and gas leakage sensors in remote places; Refrigeration.
- Wearable Devices and IoT: Application in wearable devices, such as smartwatches, IoT devices, and biomedical sensors; Microgenerators to power various components in the near future; Power supply for IoT sensors in the medium term.
- Energy Autonomous Systems: Powering sensors, remote systems, space (radioisotopes) power systems, etc.; Mention of electronic cooling and long-term power supply without maintenance.
- Space Applications: Mention of RTGs (Radioisotope Thermoelectric Generators) for space and remote power generation in special-purpose and rural domestic settings.
- Other Applications: Human-machine interface for thermal sensing and actuation, Cooling and low-temperature power generation technologies, Predictions for the future development of nanoscale heat recovery devices in industries like metallurgical, glass, or petrochemical; Use in electronic cooling, long-term power supply without maintenance, and waste heat recovery for remote power supply in IoT.

General Predictions forwarded by the experts:

- Short-term applications may include Peltier cooling.
- Medium to long-term applications include energy recovery from processes where efficiency is crucial, such as foundation industries, i.e. heavy industries.
- Long-term applications involve geothermal and solar-thermal power generation, as well as microscale thermal management.

Question 2: How will thermoelectricity impact our society? What are the pros and cons of its usage?

Summary: Experts state that thermoelectric technology offers various advantages to societal applications, including off-grid capability, durability, and the ability to generate renewable energy in hard-to-reach places. As the technology can contribute to reducing the CO₂ footprint of industries, improve energy efficiency, and enable the recovery of waste heat, these are seen as of great importance for the future of society. Impact can also be seen in promoting the energy transition and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. Despite the benefits, namely that devices have a long life and require minimal maintenance, experts

highlight some of the bottlenecks, their low efficiency, high costs, reliance on scarce materials and need for scalability as challenges that need to be addressed for widespread adoption and a significant positive impact on the environment.

Question 3: What's happening on the cutting edge of research in the field of thermoelectrics right now?

Summary: Participants referred a number of research and innovation developments in the field of thermoelectrics. These include research, innovation and development works towards optimization of known materials, to enhance reliability, efficiency, and flexibility in demanding designs and system integration. Sustainable materials and flexible devices are current crucial areas of investigation, aiming for high-performance multilayer TEs operating across large temperature ranges. Some experts see thermoelectric modules utilizing multilayer materials with a high figure of merit and proving economic viability are central concerns that need to see more investigation and efforts, as a main goal. There is a need for breakthrough technologies, and attention is turning more and more towards sustainable materials.

Other aspects of current TE research, are the emphasis in high zT materials and high performing devices, focusing on new active materials, bonding materials, and device testing. With these, the main goals are to increase efficiency, reduce manufacturing costs, and develop efficient heat transfer methods. While numerous materials show promise, integration issues and challenges in large-volume production hinder competitive pricing. Efforts also aim to lower the lattice thermal conductivity while maintaining a high-power factor, utilizing alternative materials and manufacturing methods.

Nanotechnology is also mentioned as one of the main research flagships as is the study of new materials while avoiding rare earth, toxic, or expensive elements, by employing nanostructuring or cascading devices. Flexible devices, new materials based on environmentally friendly elements, and new TEG design integration are ongoing priorities.

Question 4: How can the creation and maintenance of a thermoelectrics value chain, dependent on recovery from mining tailings, be as flexible, scalable and adaptable as possible?

Summary: The success of START as a thermoelectric technology developing project, particularly in using mining tailings, hinges on factors such as achieving high efficiency, ensuring reliable material development for thermal energy harvesting, and maintaining a flexible composition of raw materials, as suggested by experts. For the creation of the value chain, key considerations include waste reduction through mining recovery, securing a stable supply chain, and focusing on the entire process from materials production to module and system assembly. Experts mention that the scalability of the technology will depend on developing cost-effective and efficient converters and automating production, which are very important development steps. Furthermore, it is suggested that collaboration with the right partners, an open society approach, and regular interaction within the full supply chain are needed to ensure success and adaptability in the evolving community. The use of mining tailings is seen as a sensible approach to

reduce material costs in thermoelectric technology, that might give the advantage that START needs to create a unique value chain in Europe and worldwide.

Question 5: What are the potential market penetration barriers and the market opportunities for replication and market development of a tetrahedrite based TE value chain?

Summary: Mentioned market barriers include unproven performance, low efficiency and thermal stability of tetrahedrites, high processing costs and difficult process, and the absence of identified market applications. The need for high efficiency and stability in thermoelectric materials, especially for medium temperature applications like transport and heavy industries is another barrier. The importance of convincing potential markets of the utility of tetrahedrite-based TE technology is emphasized by some experts, along with the need for testing in real-world applications. Cost competitiveness, manufacturing scalability, and efficiency are identified as critical factors for successful market entry.

On the other hand, there are also market opportunities mentioned such as using tetrahedrite as a non-toxic and sustainable material, recoverable from tailings, as a unique approach, potentially pushing START forward and giving its value chain an advantage when compared to more traditional TE value chains.

Question 6: In your opinion, what is mostly missing from thermoelectrics value chains to make them an alternative to energy production?

Summary: Experts identify as main gaps in thermoelectrics value chains the lack of good performance displayed by TE materials and devices, the lack of applications across different temperature ranges, missing end-users interaction and awareness for this specific technology, the need to step up commercialization efforts and lack of more devices' prototyping, testing and implementation.

Annex – Comments from experts to the statements and questions

Statement 1: The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is the future of renewable energy and circular economy.

Agreement comments:

- I would not say it is the future, but it will take a place in the family of renewable energy. I see a brighter future in thermal energy harvesting as the mean to empower digitalization of the industry as it has remarkable advantages towards powering IIoT sensors by means of cabling or batteries.
- We proposed a combined use of waste heat for thermoelectric power and for domestic heating.
- I would prefer: "The application of thermoelectric devices to transform waste heat into energy is ONE PART OF the future of renewable energy and circular economy".
- In terms of low-grade heat harvesting, the TE technology is indeed a priority candidate, though the concern of cost-efficiency (e.g., material properties, device codesign) and sustainable manufacturing (energy consumption and carbon emission to meet UN's SDGs) are still underdeveloped.
- These efforts would be in line with the EU targets for an increasingly sustainable heavy industry by 2050 in terms of primary energy consumption and reduced CO2 emissions.
- However, the heat-to-electricity efficiency is not promising, if one wants to compare the efficiency, solely.
- TE devices will be one option in the future for converting waste heat into electricity.
- I believe it will play a role in the renewable energy field, however, is limited to specific niche applications.
- It can definitely play a role in recovering waste heat, when used in the right applications.
- CO2 emissions, Heat-to-electricity efficiency, Niche applications, Waste heat recovery.

Neutral comments:

- Thermoelectrics play a role but are only a part of the solution.
- I think TE devices will help to the energetic green transition, however I think there are other renewable energy technologies that have higher electricity production rates and efficiency.
- It may be true if the heat is really free.
- The main challenge in our society is to redesign processes such that the creation of waste heat is avoided, or - in other words - to utilize all energy generated. However in nowadays situation of huge amounts of waste heat, the transformation of waste heat will contribute significantly to clean energy and represents a form of energy circularity.

Statement 2: Sustainable thermoelectric devices would unblock the application of thermoelectrics in many fields, despite lower performance.

Agreement comments:

- Here again, I would prefer the sentence: "Sustainable thermoelectric devices would unblock PARTIALLY the application of thermoelectrics in many fields, despite lower performance" : other technical issues (as materials and devices stability, ageing effect, etc. for example) will remain.
- Indeed, the sustainability achievement (namely the impacts associated with n- and p-type origin and production) of TE is a critical step to take and to prove that is worthwhile to invest in TE development.
- When costs are associated with the source of the materials (how it is obtained, mined etc.), production methods then they will automatically be attractive for other fields.
- I completely agree the technology itself can be implemented in many fields and benefits from reliable solid-state energy conversion. This would be ideal for powering IoT sensor networks and being a reasonable alternative to Li-Ion batteries due to comparatively longer device lifetimes.
- Thermoelectrics need to be sustainable and cheap.

Neutral comments:

- In particular applications, it may be true but for many other fields, sufficient electric power can not be obtained.
- Sustainability will help, but there will still be many applications where higher performance will be necessary for adoption.
- It's a relevant point. Efficiency and power density also matters.
- The primary bottleneck for introduction of Thermoelectric devices at large scale is performance (conversion efficiency), cost and scalability. The materials used shall be well available and non toxic. The fact that the material is sustainable is secondary to the aspects above mentioned.

Statement 3: One solution-fits-all is not feasible for thermoelectric devices and applications.

Agreement comments:

- Temperature dependence of materials and devices performances, as well as design optimisation make not possible to have "One solution-fits-all".
- Correct. Several issues matter, Beyond temp range, cost factors (related to the context of use), reliability, and the possibility of customizing TEG layout require on-purpose design of TE devices.
- Applications are different in thermal load (temperatures, thermal dynamics) , and environment (air vs vacuum, harsh situations, humidity etc). Per temperature range the one material is better suited than the other. A design of a thermoelectric device shall in corporate these aspects holistically.
- The technology is very dependent on conditions thus device architecture must be considered for optimal performance.

Neutral comments:

- In the sense that TE can be applied in very different temperature ranges and it is necessary that the used materials can be stable in each operation conditions, which can be difficult to obtain. But it could happen, that a same material can operate at medium and low temperature ranges for example.
- One solution-fits-all or the generality is probably the ultimate goal for the thermoelectric community. Some solutions work well while some cannot. The physics-guided device co-design (from heat transfer and electrical impedance matching) could be a feasible way to guide the TE device fabrication and contribute to sustainable thermoelectrics.

Disagreement comments:

- There is definitely a way to design solutions that can be applied to that segment of application and thus do one fits all. Good example is the SensEver HSI from TEGnology.

Statement 4: Using tetrahedrite materials sourced from mining tailings recovery will mitigate the competition between thermoelectric and other electronic devices.

Agreement comments:

- I think that this can be a really good strategy, not only in the sustainability and waste valorization aspects, but also in the critical materials and resources management issue.

Neutral comments:

- It will help with the cost as currently to obtain the individual elements quite a lot of processing (mining, purifying etc.) is required.
- The project assumes that the production of thermoelectric materials directly from tetrahedrites can significantly reduce production costs and make the technology competitive with others. However, a clear assessment in this respect will depend on the results of the project. The processing of the minerals may turn out to be too complicated and ultimately too costly.
- It mostly depends on how use of tailing recovery impact TEG efficiency, reliability, reproducibility, etc.

Statement 5: Applications using thermoelectric devices based on tetrahedrites will be on the market by 2030.

Neutral comments:

- It depends on the effort that will be applied to develop this technology. To develop a full technology (from materials to devices) requires several years and means...

- As these materials have shown promise, key aspect is matching to the right application (source and heat flux density) in order to make an impact.
- Depends on the operating temperature and whether or not potential n-type materials are discovered.
- Perhaps for low to medium temperatures.
- Tetrahydrites (TH) is one promising option for the low to mid temperature range, using cheap and well available materials. The outcome of the project will show its performance in the given temperature range, this is too early to tell. The disadvantage of TH is the lack of a similar p-type. Furthermore it will have to compete to other mid temperature range materials such as half heuslers and skutterudites.

Disagreement comments:

- Far too optimistic. Still waiting for SKU or HH-based commercial devices, and tetrahydrite-based TEGs have already surfaced -- and the company producing them didn't survive.

Statement 6: The START innovation ecosystem would be of interest to me.

Agreement comments:

- START innovation ecosystem would be very interesting for me, presently we are active in thermoelectrics (see attached paper). We will be glad to take part in this project.
- Electronic devices produced from tailings recovery/valorization and to generate green energy from waste heat are products with a lot of interest to the sustainability and LCA areas.
- Very interesting project to contribute to sustainable thermoelectrics for a clean future.
- As an expert in thermoelectric materials and devices for waste heat recovery, I am strongly interested in the results of the project.
- START provides a linkage between the mining ecosystem, the materials processing ecosystem and the thermoelectric ecosystem, as such interesting to RGS. When the development is successful, further industrialization will have to comprise other parties, to respond to performance, cost and scalability requirements as well as to enable integration, sales and further improvement.

Question 1: What kinds of devices or applications, in the short, medium and long-term, utilise thermoelectricity?

- Wearables.
- Safety devices in industry preventing contact burns, power supplies for district heating monitoring systems, power supplies for heat exchanger monitoring systems, power supplies for pumping monitoring systems, power supplies for construction monitoring devices, power supplies for environmental sensors in remote places, power supply for gas leakage sensors in pipelines in remote places.
- Refrigeration, power generation.
- From miniature (milliwatts) to large (hundreds watts) TE modules for energy sources
- Wide range from miniature (milliwatts) to large power sources (hundreds of watts).
- Smart sensors, thermal controllers, autonomous small scale power generation.
- Waste heat recovery systems.
- Cars.
- Wearable devices.
- Industry facilities that have considerable amount of waste heat and temperature delta (furnaces, cooling stations, others); IT central systems (servers); household equipment (fridge, oven, TV, others).
- Waste heat recovery in industry.
- Human-machine interface for thermal sensing and actuation.
- Cooling and low temperature power generation technologies.
- I predict that, in the near future, the market for thermoelectric microgenerators to power various types of components, sensors or transducers, e.g. biomedical sensors, smartwatches, IoT devices, and others, will develop.
- The next stage will see the development of nm process heat recovery devices in the metallurgical, glass or petrochemical industries. In the long term, when the efficiency of thermoelectric devices is high enough, they may replace classic mechanical devices such as heat pumps and power generators.
- Peltier neck-cooler operating at room temperature (short term), Power supply for IoT sensors (medium term).
- Automotive, remote, waste heat recovery, primary power generation.
- Energy autonomous systems (sensors, remote systems, space (radioisotopes) power systems, ...).
- Industrial waste heat recovery when thermodynamic cycles cannot operate.
- Heat management (Peltier).
- Peltier coolers (chips, lasers, fridges...) and TEGs, small applications, remote sources and deep-space missions.
- RTG's (Space), Remote Power Generation (Special Purpose, Rural Domestic), Remote Sensor Power (IoT), Waste Heat recovery (Heavy Industry), Cooling (Electronics).
- Electronic cooling, long-term power supply without maintenance.
- (Waste) heat recovery, remote power supply for IOT.

- IoT sensor networks.
- In the short-term, the higher performance and cheaper Peltier cooling, in the medium-term, the power generation from waste heat in industry, ships, etc., in the long-term, geothermal and solar-thermal power generation as well as microscale thermal management will be applications of thermoelectricity.
- Micro distributed thermoelectric generation is the most promising field of application. Next to this, the thermal management combined action to achieve a high density heat exchange should be an interesting drawback of the thermoelectric device development.
- Short term, cooling/heating systems where maintenance/size is a factor. bespoke applications.
- Medium to long term. Energy recovery from processes where efficiency is important. E.g, foundation industries.
- Thermoelectricity is a niche technology mainly use in space applications.
- Automotive.

Question 2: How will thermoelectricity impact our society? What are the pros and cons of its usage?

- Pro: off grid, con: expensive.
- Enabling IoT in hard to reach places will reduce CO2 footprint of many industries with all the consequences related to it for society.
- Pros: durability, long-term viability; cons: low efficiency.
- Utilisation of waste heat.
- May provide a source for sustainable energy.
- Thermoelectrics have limited efficiency but are very sustainable, have long life-time, and scale rather easily. There is limited role for large scale power generation better served by other recovery systems, but there are clear niche applications for sensors, remote deployment, critical autonomous infrastructure, and maybe terrestrial nuclear battery type devices.
- Improve energy efficiency and reduce emissions.
- As all energy recovery systems, TE will bring new energy sources.
- Pros: work for several years, no maintenance, no mechanical part, adaptable.
- Cons: low efficiency, current TEGs for room temperature applications use rare materials.
- Save energy.
- Less batteries used, longer life of generators.
- Thermoelectricity can bring a new way to generate (renewable) energy and, consequently, reduce the electricity from fossil fuels; other important pros is that it can be applied in different applications and temperature ranges, as well as the electricity produced could be storage in batteries. However, due to its low efficiency in energy conversion, the sustainable (economic and environmental) mass production of TE devices may be compromised.
- Thermoelectricity will prevent waste of energy and resources.
- They are solid state power generation devices which if designed well will require low maintenance. However, with a complicated device stack optimizations are required not only in the active material but also in their interactions with the other layers. Their low efficiency is worrisome but if the TEG can be made cheap enough this problem can be addressed.

- I foresee a fundamentally beneficial impact of thermoelectric technology on society. In principle, the devices fall into the category of green energy sources, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, utilising waste heat and increasing the energy efficiency of technological processes.
- I do not see any disadvantages compared with alternative technologies, as long as environmentally friendly thermoelectric materials are used.
- Applied to IoT applications, the impact can be very important. I would mention the fact that there is no need for maintenance compared to alternatives. As a con, the low efficiency.
- Solid-state waste heat recovery; compact; low-efficiency.
- TE will contribute to cooling (macro and micro). COP is still borderline but there's room for improvement. Main issue is the production chain.
- Energy efficiency (better system control and waste reduction).
- The whole life cycle should be considered when evaluating a new solution (including materials production, module assembly, device assembly, product life and end-of-life).
- I do not expect any significant impact in close future. The reliability, long term service, utilization of low-potential waste heat x low efficiency for low delta T and instability for high delta T.
- Thermoelectric generation represents a complementary technology. It promotes the energy transition by enabling local energy solutions and by enabling a more efficient use of energy. Pro : Silent, no maintenance, enduring. Con : low efficiency, high cost.
- Pros: small volume, long-term operation.
- Mainly pros if based on adequate materials (available, environmentally-friendly, based on waste...).
- A reliable and sustainable power method, however heavily reliant on scarce and toxic materials and has low power density.
- If successful, thermoelectricity will change cooling systems like air-conditioning, refrigeration, and thermal management, which means that our society will be more eco-friendly. Also, local waste heat recovery will reduce the usage of fossil fuels. The problem is performance and cost. Both issues should be solved, otherwise, the impact of thermoelectricity will be minimal.
- Thermoelectricity follows the idea of recycling widely approached today. The object of recycle in this case is the wasted power: despite the low performances available for thermoelectric devices, the integration of this technology offers a natural improvement of systems efficiency. The development of devices with improved performances will increase the overall impact on society, mainly promoting a larger use of thermoelectric solution. The main issue will be to make this solution economically appealing, being the payback time for a thermoelectric system too long considering the market timing.
- Economy of scale is vital if thermoelectrics are to become mainstream. This requires a supply of cheap, secure and sustainable materials which can be efficiently processed into devices. There also needs to be a better understanding of how to utilise them into applications.
- Marginal gain of renewable energy.

Question 3: What's happening on the cutting edge of research in the field of thermoelectrics right now?

- Optimization of known materials.

- Bendable TEG designs increase reliability and efficiency of TEGs as well as its flexibility to integrate those in demanding designs.
- It is more and more recognized that very high ZT values in publications do not help to grow practical applications. We have to consider more practical needs and not only technical but sometimes emotional barriers for implementation of TE systems.
- Research on sustainable materials and flexible devices.
- High performance multilayer TE operating at large temperature range.
- Thermoelectric modules (battery) using multilayer materials with high figure of merit Z.
- Proof of economic viability of thermoelectric generators.
- Unfortunately, not enough breakthrough technology.
- Massive research.
- Attention is turning to sustainable materials.
- I'm afraid that I cannot add many relevant topics to this question, but I would say that the suitable materials for TE devices is a State of the Art research field.
- High zT materials and devices.
- From academia the focus is still on reseraching new active materials with higher figure of merit. Only recently has the focus shifted to new bonding materials and device testing (thermal ageing and cycling).
- Increasing the efficiency of thermoelectric materials and devices, reducing the manufacturing costs of these devices, and developing methods for efficient heat transfer from technological processes are currently the main areas of importance.
- Many new materials with promising performance, but none of them makes it to a device. Integration issues, and maybe large volume production problems, which the price not competitive.
- To lower lattice thermal conductivity while maintaining high power factor, by controlling point-defects, dislocations and grain-boundary coherence. Typical ball-milling is obsolete.
- Alternative materials and manufacturing methods.
- Nanotechnology still remain the workhorse, currently. Phononics will possibly complement it.
- Most focus is on new materials with high ZT.
- Probably half Heusler materials really promissing in all respects; and low price, moderate T applications.
- Improvement of materials and devices, while avoiding rare earth, toxic or expensive elements. For example nanostrucuring materials or cascading devices.
- Flexible device.
- New materials based on available, environmentally-friendly elements; TEG design and integration.
- Nano-structured metamaterials simultaneously boosting thermoelectric parameters leading to improved performance.
- Module design and manufacturing, and applications.
- Unfortunately, little is really happening... The main effort today is put in the development of thermoelectric modules based on unconventional materials, trying to improve the performances of the basic bricks of thermoelectric systems.

- Focus on device made of tellurium-free materials.

Question 4: How can the creation and maintenance of a thermoelectrics value chain, dependent on recovery from mining tailings, be as flexible, scalable and adaptable as possible?

- Make sure that the developed material is reliable. Thermal energy harvesting is not about reaching highest possible energy density or conversion factors. It is about withstanding assembly processes and operations with demanding temperature gradients and harsh environments. Thus main focus should not be on finding the most efficient material, but to ensure a complete assembly into a large scale TEG tile, that can easily be combined to a larger area to cover containers or other large surfaces or that can be fitted inbetween hot and cold surfaces withstanding humidity, vibration and temperature cycles without delaminating between the material and the packaging/conductive parts of the system.
- It depends on the ease of converting these mining tailings into a useful material.
- By achieving high figure of merit, Z (efficiency).
- These tasks depend on obtaining high figure of merit Z (efficiency).
- Mining recovery achieves two important goals: waste reduction and potentially more sustainable low-cost access to materials. In turn, this can assist the roll-out of thermoelectric technology. Note that recovery of elements from consumer electronics waste should also be considered.
- Guarantee the source of materials supply.
- If possible, it will increase the added value of thermoelectric generators.
- I think it is really important that the available mining tailings can provide TE base materials with uniformity/equivalent properties, that these materials can be processed by similar conditions and parameters, and that these mining tailings recovered materials are available in feasible amounts.
- Flexible composition of raw materials.
- Finetuned supply chain will bring together interested industrial partners who were not directly connected to thermoelectrics and bring a device architecture to market that can be quickly adapted to different application needs.
- The scalability of the technology will essentially depend on the immediate results of the project - i.e. the development of sufficiently cheap and efficient converters. The next step will be to scale up and automate production to reduce human labour input. This process will require, as in the case of similar technologies (e.g. photovoltaics), the development of fully automated large-scale production technology and therefore significant investment.
- Thermoelectrics has historically been hindered by cost. Using mine tailings can greatly reduce the effective cost of the materials.
- Secure sourcing from different mines (and tackle the challenge to keep consistent TE properties whatever the material source).
- Think about the whole process (including module assembly and system assembly), not just about TE materials production.
- It will need to be an open society, where evolution of the community and solutions can be accommodated. It shall represent the full supply chain. It shall regularly interact to remain looking at the large picture.
- In principle appears to be a sensible use of materials.

- The major issue of thermoelectrics is the cost, mainly material cost. Mining tailings can contribute to the reduction of materials' cost.

Question 5: What are the potential market penetration barriers and the market opportunities for replication and market development of a tetrahedrite based TE value chain?

- Performance and thermal stability of tetrahedrites.
- Identify the market applications. There is nothing specific to tetrahedrite based TE, if the applications for TEH have been identified and accepted in industry.
- Maintenance of functionality and reproducibility.
- The present low efficiency.
- The limited efficiency in energy conversion.
- Tetrahedrites have not yet a proven track record for functioning modules in the commercial world. They might breach the temperature barrier limitation of current commercial modules though.
- Need for high efficiency and thermally and mechanically stable material.
- Medium temperature applications such as transport, heavy industries.
- Processing technology.
- I'm not an expert in this subject, but I think an opportunity is that tetrahedrite can be a new and different material comparing with Bi, Pb and Te; non-toxic and more sustainable if tetrahedrite can be recovered from tailings. I think market barriers are related with processing costs and efficiency.
- Penetration barriers are low efficiency and high cost.
- Sustainability and cost-effectiveness.
- Market niches that could benefit from thermoelectric devices are not aware of this option. In this field we have to go out and convince them of the utility of this power generation technology. furthermore, tetrahedrite is a novel material which is interesting from a cost-perspective but has still not been tested in an application setting. Once that is done, it can be used a case study for marketing purposes.
- One major obstacle is the lack of devices, such as thermoelectric generators, capable of implementing tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric modules for large-scale use. In parallel with the technologies to produce the materials, heat recovery and conversion devices should be developed.
- Probably, cost issues, and manufacturing scalability.
- High enough performance for low enough cost.
- The same hindering manufacturing in EU. No market, no killer applications, high manufacturing costs, volatile market.
- Low efficiency compared to other heat to power solutions.
- Unproven longlife durability.
- Unproven final product low cost (low-cost TE material does not mean low-cost products).
- Effectivity/price ratio.
- The main barrier for terrestrial application will be performance, cost and scalability compared to incumbent technologies such as diesel generator, solar+batteries and fuel cell technologies.

- Efficiency.
- Producing sustainable and effective fabrication protocol to process materials. Bottoms-up chemical synthesis could be of great interest.
- Cost.
- The main barrier to the market penetration is, as always, the cost competitiveness. Reliability could be an opportunity to attack this limit, but to reach the final user the technology has to offer unique solutions to critical problems or to provide competitive performances at a lower price. Tetrahedrites could allow a production cost reduction next to the advantage of a mining wastes issue management (this is a plus of START project), providing a multiple benefit probably helpful in pushing the solution suggested over the costs barrier.
- Sulphide instability.